

Doctors of Debt: Cutting or Capping the Public Service Loan Forgiveness Program (PSLF) hurts physicians in training

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ABSTRACT Growing medical student debt has increased reliance on government loan forgiveness plans like the Public Service Loan Forgiveness Program (PSLF). Evidence suggests that delayed financial gratification in addition to stagnant resident salaries has exacerbated problems related to salary gaps and burnout. Although capping the PSLF may help curb national debt in the United States Department of Education, in the case of medical students, this policy is misplaced. The objective of this review is to discuss the implications of capping the PSLF program on medical student education. Policy reform should focus on halting medical school tuition hikes and increasing resident physician salaries.

KEYWORDS: Debt; Education; Healthcare; Public Service Loan Forgiveness Program

Introduction

The Public Service Loan Forgiveness Program (PSLF) continues to be the number one choice of repayment plans for medical students nationwide. Policies that limit loan forgiveness are misplaced in the case of medical education, because of the delayed financial gratification secondary to residency and fellowship training. Instead, policies should focus on increasing reimbursements for residents and fellows, and the cap is staggering tuition hikes for medical students.

Public Service Loan Forgiveness Program and Medical Education Debt

The PSLF offers loan forgiveness after working ten years in a public service position. Borrowers must pay 120 non-consecutive monthly payments while working full-time, at least

30 hours per week, in a public service position (Public Service Loan Forgiveness Program 2015). Only qualified public service positions are eligible, including those who work in a 501(c)(3) non-profit, government, or a not-for-profit organisation. About 25% of the American workforce qualifies for PSLF, but a majority of those enrolled in the program are graduate students, who have no limit on how much they can borrow (Public Service Loan Forgiveness Program 2015; Josuweit 2016). Currently, over 431,000 people are enrolled in PSLF with the number growing rapidly (Delisle 2016).

PSLF is widely seen as an incentivising program for graduate students interested in public service jobs. For physicians-in-training, this is especially relevant as 75% of US hospitals are non-profits or public entities (Friedman et al. 2016). Approximately 95% of medical students from 2010 to 2013 were eligible for PSLF (Friedman et al. 2016). Overall, the median debt of those enrolled in PSLF is \$60,000, but nearly 30% of borrowers have over \$100,000 in debt (Friedman et al. 2016). On average, PSLF represents about \$150,000 in savings for primary care physicians (Friedman et al. 2016). In a 2014 survey of medical graduates up to 62% intended to use the PSLF, making it the number one choice of repayment plans among medical students (Friedman et al. 2016). It is no wonder that participation in the program among physicians has grown substantially, 21.2% since 2010 (Friedman et al. 2016).

When PSLF was initially enacted, it was thought only a select few would qualify; however, policymakers failed to recognise

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that those who qualified had the most significant loan balances overall. The reality is that the program largely benefits highly educated borrowers with graduate degrees, such as medical students. Under the Obama administration, the House Budget Committee proposed a cap on PSLF at \$57,500 for all students. This cap would save an estimated \$12 billion in loan forgiveness over the next ten years (Josuweit 2016). President Trump's current 2018 budget proposes to cut the PSLF program altogether completely. Moreover, this October 2017 marks the first time that PSLF loans will be forgiven.

Policy Details: PSLF Cap hurts Medical Students and Resident Physicians

By the year 2030, the Association of American Medical Colleges (AAMC) projects that there will be a shortage of physicians by 40,800 to 104,900 (Beach 2015). As the population ages and more than 32 million more Americans have health insurance, this shortage is anticipated among primary care physicians (Beach 2015). The ultimate goal is to train 130,000 physicians to meet the increased need by 2025 (Beach 2015).

As a result, medical schools have increased enrollment, but concerns over the rising cost of medical education debt loom. An estimated 86% of medical school graduates have incurred education debt with the amount increasing yearly (Medical Student Debt). A study by Friedman et al. found that 11% of the 2011 graduating class had debt over \$150,000, while more than 50% of the 2013 graduating class had debt over \$150,000 (Friedman et al. 2016).

The American Medical School Association reports that over the past 20 years the median medical school tuition and fees increased by 312% for public schools and 165% for private schools (Medical Student Debt). In 2003, the median tuition was \$16,322 for public schools and \$34,550 for private medical schools (Weinstein and Wolfe 2010). For 2016-2017, the median yearly tuition was \$31,343 for public medical school and \$52,500 for private medical school (Medical Student Debt). The sharp increase in tuition does not include debt incurred by interest and additional fees. The average medical graduate has over \$175,000 in debt, which is only going to increase in years to come (Friedman et al. 2016).

Further, rising medical school debt disproportionately impacts students who are low income, which may be deterred from attending medical school in the first place. In a recent national survey, the cost of attending medical school was the number one reason why qualified applicants chose not to apply (Friedman et al. 2016). Minority students represent approximately 25% of the US population, but only make up 12% of medical students in the US (Medical Student Debt). Overall, they are more likely to enter into primary care than their White counterparts (Medical Student Debt). Thus, the debt crisis serves to exacerbate the shortage of minority physicians and limits improvement in patient care in underserved communities (Medical Student Debt).

Challenges to PSLF: Delayed Financial Gratification and Burn Out

Those who support the PSLF cap argue that medical students, like many other graduate students, may perceive the unrestricted loans as an opportunity to borrow irresponsibly. Proponents often cite the scenario that a medical student who knows that their loans will be forgiven may choose to live less frugally during their training and spend loan money recklessly (Delisle

2016). On the contrary, in a study among second-year medical students concerning medical debt, 48% said they had accepted the reality of their high debt and felt responsible and able to repay it (Phillips et al. 2016). Capping the PSLF goes against the notion that medical students spend recklessly knowing their loans will eventually be forgiven.

The rising cost of PSLF among graduate students is one of the main reasons to cap loan forgiveness. Advocates for capping PSLF fail to consider the length and delayed financial gratification of medical training overall. To be a board-certified physician, students must complete four years of college, four years of medical school, and 3-7 years of residency, with an optional 1-3 years of fellowship training after residency. At a minimum, most students can only start working as an attending physician after 11 years of training.

Financing Options

Thankfully, the PSLF cap has not garnered much traction in Congress. However, it has reinvigorated the conversation about medical school debt and how to best address rising tuition costs. Some opponents of PSLF like President Trump have advocated for entirely repealing PSLF and having borrowers enrol in other loan programs (Delisle 2016). Some suggest basing repayment plans based on salary, but there would be no public service incentive component. The monthly repayment amount would also skyrocket once a resident achieved attending physician status.

Still, others have advocated for reform of the entire medical education system as a way to combat rising debt. Currently, the fourth year of medical school revolves around interviewing and auditioning for residency positions at various hospitals (Emanuel and Fuchs 2012). Decreasing medical school by just one year would save 25% in graduate medical tuition. This proposal must not be oversimplified, as it could drastically limit the financial resources of many existing medical schools. Also, it would significantly reduce the number of contact hours students have with patients.

Nevertheless, Texas Tech School of Medicine has adopted this model, while others like Duke School of Medicine have restructured their curriculum to suit students' clinical or research interests (Emanuel and Fuchs 2012). Internationally, medical schools in the United Kingdom offer a combined undergraduate and medical degree in six years rather than eight (Emanuel and Fuchs 2012).

In addition to decreasing the years in medical school, Graduate Medical Education (GME) needs to consider refinancing the salaries of underpaid residents and fellows alike. Resident physicians work up to 80 hours per week for about \$50,000 per year before taxes are deducted. This amounts to less than \$10 per hour and does not accurately reflect the value of a resident's work in a medical team or hospital setting while encouraging burn out. Reforming GME rather than capping or eliminating PSLF is more reasonable and necessary in the long term.

Conclusion

As medical schools increase enrollment in response to the anticipated physician shortage, concerns over the rising cost of medical education debt loom. A proposed cap on the PSLF threatens to disincentivise medical student education. Further, stagnant resident salaries continue to delay financial gratification for physicians. The proposed cap on loan forgiveness ignores the

current realities experienced by both medical students and resident physicians. Instead of capping PSLF, policymakers should consider halting rising medical student tuition costs and reform GME stagnant salaries – or else they will become Doctors of Debt.

Declarations of Interest:

The authors report no declarations of interest.

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